

Peer tutoring analysis in inclusive classes using character education approach

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to analyze peer tutoring in inclusive classes with character education approaches for elementary students. The target of this study were 30 teachers, 525 students, and 98 disabled students from nine elementary schools in East Sumba Regency. This research focused on changing the character of students with special needs or not using peer tutoring methods that are modified with various learning techniques. The results showed a change in the character of students with special needs and not with the peer tutoring method. Thus, peer tutoring can be recommended in improving learning skills and forming student character. Future studies are expected to show how peer tutoring shapes students' emotional intelligence in inclusive classes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

UNESCO in 1997 and UNICEF in 2007 brought up the concept of education for all those based on human rights in the protection of children [1]. To achieve an independent education, justice, happiness, respect, and emotional development of every child are needed without discrimination [2]. One example is the inclusive education carried out in the UK providing special services to children and adolescents who experience physical and mental disabilities [3]. Inclusive education in Indonesia began in 2003 [4], [5], intended to provide opportunities for students with special needs, both those who have special limitations or intelligence to be able to enjoy the learning process as students without disabilities or disabled ones. Moreover, inclusive education has been implemented in several developed and developing countries, including in Brunei Darussalam, New Zealand, Taiwan, South Korea, China, Malaysia, Thailand, Finland, Japan, and several other countries. Regular schools are committed to providing inclusive education for students with special needs [6].

Inclusive education gives space for teachers to not discriminate against students and can accept differences that exist in the school environment, especially in the classroom [7]. This is different from inclusive education in Japan, which is something unique in the world and is different from inclusive education in the USA which prefers cognition. Students with special needs in Japan are treated well, fairly, and do service with joy just like normal students without feeling any different and are invited to collaborate

in developing creative ideas. Furthermore, students with disabilities are separated according to the competition [8], [9]. Respect as fellow human beings, and fair because they have the same right to enjoy quality education. However, in reality, students with special needs are done unfairly [10]. 2010 data inform that students with special needs are often harassed in classrooms and public schools and harm their image. As many as 70% experienced violence from different cultural aspects [11], [12]. Students with special needs experience physical and psychological violence at regular schools. The 2014 data of research in England show that male students experienced physical violence by 96.2%, female students by 99.5%, in addition to psychological violence for male students by 63.6% and female students by 65.2% [13]. Data of 2018 informs that physical violence to disabled persons is 20.4% and sexual violence is 13.7% [14]. This is due to teachers and schools feeling inconvenienced because they drain more energy to find the right ideas so that students are helped in learning and creating productive things. The teacher culture of Eastern Indonesia is distinct from the culture of a teacher in western Indonesia. This can be seen that teachers in Eastern Indonesia misuse students because of geographical aspects that have become the main factor.

On the contrary, teachers in western Indonesia are friendly, polite, and gentle in the service so that students feel more comfortable. In the same way, education in Australia, which prioritizes the needs of students in terms of behavior, language, religion, and culture in society [15], [16]. The daily violence that occurs is usually verbal, physical, and non-verbal. For example, rejection from teachers and other students, labeling as "stupid", beatings, even intimidation [17], [18]. The students with special needs treatment need to be changed from a pattern of violence to a more humane pattern so that it feels safe [19], [20]. Teachers as managers in the classroom can direct students to learn to respect social differences, instill a sense of empathy, and others through social education to cultivate character value in the classroom towards the characterized golden generation of Indonesia by 2045 [21], [22].

Character education can be in the form of written or unwritten things that are taught in formal and non-formal education. Formally, character education has been integrated into the curriculum according to the current development and the needs of the school [23]. The character of students can be formed from the social environment at home and even schools that are used in gaining knowledge [24]. Interaction in learning can form positive behaviors, self-confidence, and feelings that have an impact on teacher actions towards students [25]. So that teaching of character values becomes important in inclusive education, especially in the classroom. Inclusive class means students with special needs, such as students with visual impairment, hearing impairment, difficulty in speaking, physical impairment, as well as students who are slow to learn, gifted, or other learning difficulties mix with regular students to learn together in the classroom [26]. Moreover, inclusive classes facilitate all students to get learning that is tailored to the unique abilities, and development of each student [27].

Formation of character in the classroom can be done through learning design by giving attention to the selection of learning models that have an impact on character formation [28], [29]. Cooperative learning has an impact on the formation of student character and social cooperation [30], [31], its use in groups, and structurally [32], [33]. Peer tutoring is classified as cooperative learning, where students become learning partners by pairing and grouping patterns and the teacher acts as a facilitator [34]. Peer tutoring is student-centered learning-based, with its emphasis on effective and efficient learning so that all students can achieve mastery learning, especially in teaching and shaping characters [34]-[36]. These characters in learning by using the method of peer tutoring can be achieved when students help each other in the learning process in class, so that there is a change in character in students who have special needs or not. From the explanation, the purpose of the study is to analyze peer tutoring in inclusive classes with a character education approach for elementary students.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is action research. The research was conducted with several stages including, 1) training, 2) workshops, 3) mentoring for classroom teachers in schools implementing inclusive education so that the teacher can hold inclusive learning in the classroom to shape the character of students. This action research was designed according to a model developed by Kemmis & McTaggart namely PAOR [37]. This study uses a peer-tutoring approach developed by O'Shea & O'Shea [38].

The study was conducted in Rindi District, East Sumba Regency, East Nusa Tenggara Province. There were 30 persons from 9 schools, SDN Kamalawatar, SDN Nusa, SDI Kandara, SDN Tanalingu, SDN Matawai, SDI Kayuri, SD Masehi Praiyawang, SDI Tanaraing, and SDI Tapil. The number of students was 525 people from classes 1, 2, and 3. Students with special needs were 98. The study was conducted in Rindi District due to the great number of students with special needs, both physical and mental.

The observation instrument was designed to obtain data related to changes in attitude, teachers' reflection, and students' testimony. Other instruments were in the form of interviews with teachers about

knowledge before and after training, changes experienced by teachers before and after learning, and the condition of students as well as students' responses when implementing peer tutoring. After completing the training, the students continued their learning for one semester with the materials and test instruments that have been developed by the teacher. Observation sheet in the form of questions that have been developed to check the implementation of training and learning activities in class for one semester that was checked by the observer and evaluated with the teachers. First, the planning stage of determining focus and identifying problems. Based on the identification results, alternative problem solving is determined. In the planning stage, things are as follows. 1) Designing the training and workshops to be implemented in action, 2) Selecting and determining workshop and training material, 3) Developing learning resources. 4) Developing an action evaluation format, 5) Developing an observation format, 6) Developing classroom learning. Second, action and observation. At the action stage, the teachers will be trained to implement the results of the training in learning in inclusive classes to shape student character through peer-tutoring methods. In the process of observation, it is divided into two parts namely observation of the teacher and observation of students. Observations are carried out using the developed observer format, which functions as an instrument of assessment of teacher actions and changes in student behavior. Third, the reflection consists of a) evaluation of the actions taken by the teacher. Action's evaluation includes three parts, namely the quality, quantity, and time of each type of action, b) evaluation of the results of actions, namely changes in behavior in students. Evaluation results include changes that occur, the quality of change, the impact of changes, c) Improvement of the implementation of actions based on the results of the evaluation to be implemented in the next cycle.

Other data collection was done by survey techniques using the type of close-ended items, in-depth interviews with teachers and students. The questions were structured, open, and flexible. Focus group discussions were conducted on teacher groups intending to see the achievements and the similarity of changes that occur in the character of the teacher and students. Observations were conducted for students both in pairs and individually. Analysis of documents was in the form of teacher notes related to the changes experienced by students. Also, besides training documentation, the implementation of classroom learning in the form of things developed by students with disabilities was considered.

Analysis of research data was in the form of the mapping of students with special needs and the number of teachers to be trained. Additionally, from the available information, it detailed the changes in behaviors of students with special needs before and after the implementation of peer tutoring and the implementation of learning for one semester. All data collected was developed in a qualitative descriptive form to detail and explain the results of the data.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Cycle one

In the first cycle, in the form of a planning stage, it identifies the problem carried out to determine the focus of the problem. The problem faced is the character of students both regular and special needs in inclusive classes that have not been properly formed. To answer these problems, teachers need to be given knowledge, skills to organize learning in inclusive classes. The results of preliminary observations and interviews with 30 teachers and 9 school principals, showed that teachers found it difficult to teach characters to shape the character of students in inclusive classes due to the lack of teachers' knowledge in carrying out learning in inclusive classes. Furthermore, teachers' behavior in interacting with students with special needs is dissatisfaction. Teachers still treated students with special needs as obstacles in teaching and as well as becoming an additional burden for teachers. Based on these problems, the initial solution before the teachers teach character and shape students' character, they need to be given awareness, knowledge, understanding, and skills to change patterns of interaction with students with special needs and manage learning in inclusive classes. Teachers' behavior for conducting training and workshops can be seen in Table 1.

Training and workshops related to the management of inclusive learning were determined as the initial activities of the planning stage. In planning training and workshops, preliminary studies were conducted at primary schools as the target of research. The results of the preliminary study obtained data related to teaching problems in the class related to attitudes, the ability of teachers to manage inclusive classes is low, including teaching related to characters in class. Data from the results of the preliminary study was analyzed and then developed to design training and workshops related to the use of strategies and materials provided.

The material presented in training and workshops was divided into two stages namely; 1) Training related to awareness in organizing inclusive education. In this training the material provided was; (i) the concept of children, children's rights and child protection, (ii) diversity of students, (iii) children with special needs, (iv) the teacher's role in supporting the child's tasks and development, (v) the ethics of interacting with children, (vi) inclusive education. The selection of these materials was based on the results of a preliminary

study showing that schools accept children with special needs for education, but they are still students who are treated unfairly, consequently they often experience violence; 2) Training related to pedagogical competence. The material included; (i) profile of inclusive school teachers, (ii) assessment of children with special needs, (iii) learning methods and techniques for inclusive classes, (iv) syllabus and learning implementation plan for inclusive classes, (v) individual learning plans for students, (vi) planning and manufacturing, (vii) designing an inclusive learning environment. Referring to the first training above, the selection of material in this training was based on the study results showing that the teachers performed low ability to design learning in inclusive classes, including designing character-based learning, which has an impact on the character of students who are less well-formed.

In the planning stage, the preparation of learning resources was intended to be used by teachers as guidance for organizing character-based inclusive education by applying the peer tutoring method. The next step is developing an evaluation instrument to measure affective learning outcomes (characters) using the peer tutoring method. The next is the development of an observation instrument for the implementation of the peer teaching method in teaching character. Finally is the development of a plan for implementing learning in the classroom. The development of the design of the implementation of learning in character-based classes was carried out in the form of workshops and conducted together with the teachers to develop inclusive and character-based learning plans with peer tutoring methods to be applied in classroom learning.

This planning stage produced; 1) Teachers' knowledge and awareness in organizing inclusive education, and how to interact with students with special needs in the classroom; 2) Teachers' knowledge and skills in managing inclusive learning in the classroom; 3) Inclusive learning implementation plans for character building based on the peer tutoring method. The Second stage is action and observation. At this stage, the action taken was the implementation of the use of peer tutoring methods in the classroom learning process for students by the teacher. The implementation of this method focused on checking changes in students' character. The action taken by the teacher was based on the implementation of a learning plan that had been prepared at the planning stage, while the observation process was carried out to see students' reactions and their impact on character changes.

The results of the implementation of the action in teaching the characters in inclusive classes through the method of peer tutoring on the learning themes of five third grade elementary schools with the first and second sub-themes. There were 60% of teachers who had not been able to implement peer-tutoring methods to teach characters in inclusive classes well. The teacher has difficulty implementing the learning methods that have been designed in the learning design. As a result, there has not been a change in behavior that can shape the character of students in inclusive classes. 40% of teachers who were quite successful in implementing peer tutoring methods in the classroom made only 68% of their students show behavioral changes after three meetings in the first sub-theme.

Six teachers who were unable to implement the peer-tutoring method in shaping student character properly were connected to difficulties of providing understanding to students related to students with special needs in their classrooms. The reason was that students were accustomed to neglect their classmates with special needs. Students with special needs were considered as a distractor. Then, there were found difficulties when applying methods that encourage regular students to interact with students with special needs. Otherwise, four teachers who successfully made their students begin to show behavioral change was due to the small number of students in the class, so the use of methods was able to encourage behavior change. In the first cycle of action and observation, the activities carried out eight meetings. Teachers' ability to learn design, can be shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Teachers' behavior for conducting training and workshops

Before	Teachers behavior		After	Percentage (%)
	Percentage (%)			
Committing violence (psychic, psychology, verbal, non-verbal)	100	Stop violence (psychic, psychology, verbal, non-verbal)		87
Grumpy	95	Patient		70
Verbally harsh	97	Well-versed		85
Refusing students with special needs	90	Accepting students with special needs		80

The results of learning reflection in the first cycle show; one, the evaluation of the planning stages, namely, the provision of knowledge and skills for teachers in implementing peer tutoring methods in inclusive classes through training and workshops have not been able to show significant results. Several factors cause, among others; 1) There was a change in teacher behavior in interacting with students with special needs; 2) The teachers' awareness in the implementation of inclusive learning in the classroom

increased; 3) Teacher s’ knowledge and skills related to inclusive learning management increased; 4) Teachers’ knowledge related to learning methods for teaching in inclusive classrooms increased; 5) Teachers’ knowledge and skills in inclusive classroom management increased.

Table 2. Teachers’ ability to learning design

Before	Teachers behavior		After	Percentage (%)
	Percentage (%)			
Unable to assessment student with special need	100	Able to assessment		90
Difficult to develop an inclusive lesson plan	100	Convenient to develop an inclusive lesson plan		100
Difficult to select an applicable method based on students' need	70	Convenient for selecting an applicable method based on students' need		100
Difficult to design attractive instructional media	60	Convenient to design attractive instructional media		90
Unable to setting inclusive classroom	20	Able to setting inclusive classroom		100

Second, evaluation of the stages of action and observation showed that; the difficulty of the teacher's implementation of the peer tutoring method in learning was caused by; first, the teachers’ adjustment to changes in the use of teaching methods, the change from the use of conventional learning methods to the use of active methods. Second, the limitations of teachers in using techniques in learning that support the implementation of peer tutoring methods. Third, the teachers were in the process of transitioning the formation of perspectives related to students with special needs. Fourth, regular students in the class had difficulty changing the outlook related to students with special needs in class. The reason was that they were accustomed to seeing students with special needs as students who are stupid and have no abilities. Fifth is a student with special needs, not yet confident because they are accustomed to being considered incapable and experiencing violence. So it can be said that in the implementation of the first cycle there have not been any significant changes in student character. Based on the results of reflection, the improvements made in the second cycle namely; 1) There needs to be direct guidance to teachers in implementing the peer teaching method. This directed assistance is focused on the process of supporting teachers to implement learning methods, using learning techniques that encourage the formation of student characters; 2) To fix up the implementation of related actions according to the design of the implementation of learning in class results of reflection.

3.2. Cycle two

Planning the second cycle is based on the results of the reflection of the first cycle. There has not been a significant change in the character of students taught using the peer-teaching method in inclusive classroom settings caused by the low ability of teachers to implement learning using the method. In this cycle, continuous assistance was given to the teacher in implementing the peer tutoring method. The second cycle of planning stages began with mentoring to teachers in implementing the peer tutoring method. The mentoring plan started by choosing the right learning techniques that the teacher could use to teach students character. Then, together with the teachers to develop learning using peer tutoring methods by including various learning techniques that could foster student character. Stages of action and observation were carried out to see the level of change in character in students. First is the stages of action; implementing learning using peer tutoring with various techniques. At the stage of the action, students were trained to have good characters. In teaching these characters, the teacher used a peer tutoring method that had been modified with various learning techniques. Peer tutoring with techniques of (a) games, (b) project, (c) demonstration, can be shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Peer tutoring with techniques of: (a) games, (b) project, (c) demonstration

As shown in Table 3, based on observations related to actions taken by the teacher, regular students slowly showed changes in behavior. The relationship between regular students and students with special needs changed. The second character types of students for regular and special needs who showed a positive change. Good characters grew in students such as patience, mutual respect, communicativeness, working together, creative, responsible, confident, accepting differences, friendly and empathetic. The application of learning using peer tutoring methods using various learning techniques has an impact on student change. In the second cycle, the action and observation activities were carried out during the twelve classroom learning meetings on various subjects except for religious subjects. Types of disabilities for students with special needs, is displayed in Table 4.

Table 3. The behavior change of regular students

Before	The behavior of students		After	Percentage (%)
	Percentage (%)			
Mocking friends	100	Stop mocking friends		82.3
Hitting friends with special needs	92	Stop hitting friends with special needs		98
Reluctant to help friends with special needs	95	Eager to help friends with special needs		88
Hesitant to cooperate with friends with special needs	100	Confident to cooperate with friends with special needs		93
Disregard friends with special needs	93	regard friends with special needs		96.5
Averse to share with friends with special needs	88	Eager to share with friends with special needs		90
Reject with friends with special needs	86	Accept friends with special needs		93.7

Table 4. Types of disabilities for students with special needs

Type of disabilities	Total	Percentage (%)
Speech impairment	2	2.04
Physical Impairment	3	3.06
Deaf	2	2.04
Nearsighted	1	1.02
Slow learner	38	38.78
Difficulties in learning	41	41.84
Hearing impairment	5	5.10
Epilepsy	4	4.08
Down syndrome	2	2.04

The results of reflection in the second cycle showed that there was a change in student character. The behavior changes of special needs students can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. The behavior changes of special needs students

Before	The behavior of teachers		After	Percentage (%)
	Percentage (%)			
Feeling ashamed to make friends	95	Proud to make friends		100
Reluctant to receive assistance from friends	78.6	Enthusiastic receive assistance from friends		100
Feeling embarrassed to ask friends if not understanding teacher explanation	98	Comfortable to ask friends if not understanding teacher explanation		100
Hesitant to cooperate with friends	84	Confident to cooperate with friends		100
Resistant to listen to friends' opinion	80	Accepting friends' opinion		100
Embarrassed to express an opinion	100	Comfortable to express an opinion		100
Disinterested to show strength	83.7	Eager to show strength		100
Impatient in listening to an explanation	90	Patient in listening to an explanation		97
Embarrassed to ask for assistance	98	Desire to ask for assistance		100
Embarrassed to tell that cannot do something, then getting help	100	Eager to tell that cannot do something, then getting help		100

Changes occurred in regular students and those with special needs. Changes to teacher guidance and learning design with peer tutoring methods using various techniques showed a significant improvement in this cycle. Thirty teachers in nine elementary schools were able to implement peer-tutoring methods to teach character to students. 90.8% of regular students showed positive character changes, similar changes were experienced by 99.7% of students with special needs, speech disorder and hearing impairment, limitations in speaking and listening. However, they had advantages in drawing and doing things that are psychomotor by

paying attention to the details of the examples shown, so that work was completed faster and neater and created in original ideas as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 (a). Students with speech and listening disorders creating geometry; (b) Students who are slow in learning capable to create handcraft

Information is intended to provide a comprehensive learning experience and overview related to how peer tutoring shapes the character of students in inclusive classes. The results show that both regular and special students lead to better character changes and an indirect effect on changes in teacher character. Peer tutoring allows students to; learning certain skills, involving all in learning and increasing practice about behavior [38]. This statement is in line with the results shown, seen from the change in behavior by students. Other information comes from students, who are slow in learning, children to be annoying with friends, unfocused, and difficult to understand learning, difficulty learning concepts such as helping friends to work on tasks that require motor skills [39], [40]. Other research shows that peer tutoring develops student attitudes such as being open, active, responsible [33]. The use of peer tutoring methods in inclusive classroom settings for students in rural areas has a positive impact. Using various learning techniques together with peer-tutoring qualified to encourage and shape the character of students. Regular students and students with special needs both experience significant changes out of a total of 199 third-grade students in nine elementary schools in Rindi sub-district, East Sumba district, there are 22% of students with special needs. 50% of these students had barriers in the form of learning difficulties, 20% are students who were slow in learning, 18% were students with communication difficulties and were slow in learning, while the rest was students with impaired learning difficulties (low vision), hearing difficulty (low hearing), and epilepsy.

Barriers owned by students with disabilities are insecure, shy, angry, self-doubting, afraid, nervous, pessimistic, and anxious. Contrary, regular students discern students with special needs as trouble, undependable, unsociable, obstacle, and harassment objects. As a result, learning activities become difficult. The demographic bonus, as students in remote villages, also contributes to the establishment of their character [41]; especially the attitude of treating people with special needs. Apart from that as a follow-up impact of the limitations that exist on students with special needs, the teacher also considers them as an additional burden in the learning process in class. The results of other studies indicate that peer tutoring provides good social interaction results [42]. This statement by the results of research shows that the peer tutoring method in learning shapes social interactions and encourages changes in students' character. The inclusive classroom setting in this study uses the peer tutoring method, allowing students to celebrate diversity and accept other students' differences, thereby changing the patterns of interaction between students and shaping their character. Inclusive classes encourage each student to respect other students and treat them as worthy neighbors [43]. Furthermore, peer tutoring also provides space for students to break the chain of obstacles in the development of student character that has occurred so far [44]. Regular students become open minded, friendly, respectful, patient, helpful, and responsible to students with special needs. This helps encourage students with special needs to develop their good character.

4. CONCLUSION

All students who participated in this study showed positive character changes. Teaching characters that are included systematically in the design of learning gives good results for character improvement. Teaching character is important to be done systematically because teaching character to students is as important as teaching knowledge and skills. This study also indicates that there is a change in teacher characters. Teacher character transformation provides a virtuous example. Appropriate examples are needed in a variety of character teaching in the classroom, especially related to relationships with students with

special needs who study in public schools in inclusive classroom settings. This research also shows that peer tutoring used in learning cannot stand alone but must be implemented with various learning techniques such as games, demonstrations, recitation, simulation, socio-drama, role-playing, and project. This research contributes to helping the school community be confident in developing student character through peer tutoring and learning to process character building through systematic learning as teachers, regular students, and students with special needs. Future studies are expected to show how peer tutoring shapes students' emotional intelligence in inclusive classes.

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